

OCAP[®] PRINCIPLES

DATASHEET FOR INDIGENOUS DATASETS

DATASET IDENTIFICATION

Dataset Title:

Brief description of dataset contents:

Primary language(s) represented:

Time period covered:

MOTIVATION & PURPOSE

1. For what purpose was this dataset created?
2. What specific community goals does this dataset serve?

3. How does this dataset support community self-determination?

CREATION & FUNDING

1. Who funded the creation of this dataset?

2. How will sustainability of the dataset be funded and for how long?

OWNERSHIP: COMMUNITY COLLECTIVE RIGHTS

1. Which Indigenous community owns this dataset?

2. Who created the dataset on their behalf?

3. What community members, knowledge holders, or cultural authorities were involved?

4. How are individual vs. collective ownership rights balances?

5. What consent and approval processes were followed? (e.g., individual, institutional, family, community, traditional authority)

ACCESS: COMMUNITY-CONTROLLED DISTRIBUTION

1. What are the different access levels? (e.g., community-only, restricted, research, public)

2. How is access controlled?

3. How do external parties request access and what criteria guide access?

4. What are approved purposes and what uses are explicitly prohibited?

5. How can consent be modified or revoked?

POSSESSION: PHYSICAL & DIGITAL CONTROL

1. Where is the data physically and digitally housed?

2. What is the format of the dataset?

3. What technical processing was done and who was involved?

4. How does the community maintain control over copies and backups?

COMMUNITY APPROVAL & GOVERNANCES

Primary community representative name and title _____

Next scheduled review date and process:

SIGNATURES & COMMITMENTS

Community representative name, title

Date

Commitment (type below): "I commit to honor OCAP® principles and community governance authority."

External partner name, organization.

Date

Commitment (type below): "I commit to follow community governance and OCAP® principles."

This framework is a living document that evolves with community needs. Community authority and Indigenous data sovereignty supersede all other considerations in the governance and use of this dataset.

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